

STRUCTURAL OPTIMIZATION OF FOUR-WHEELER CHASSIS

Kiran B N

M. Tech Student, Department of Mechanical Engineering,
PES University, Bangalore 560085, India

Jyothisna K Moorthy

Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering,
PES University, Bangalore 560085, India

ABSTRACT

A chassis, the main part of an automobile, carries all mechanical components and must be strong enough to withstand instant and fatigue loads, high friction, and vibration under various conditions. It requires high cross section strength and adequate bending stiffness, making steel the most commonly used material for automotive chassis production. This research aims to build a high strength to weight ratio truck chassis among various materials like Mild steel, ASTM A148 Gr 80–50 mild steel, Structural Steel AISI 1015, ASTM A710 Steel, and High Carbon Steel AISI 1065. The chassis model is constructed with two C-section side rails and rectangular cross members, using ANSYS Parametric Design Language (APDL). Here cross sectional dimension of the side rails and different steel materials are considered as the design parameters, and Taguchi DOE method is used for optimization. FEA analysis and model parameterization are done in APDL. This study uses APDL-based FEA to analyze stress and deformation parameters, Signal to Noise ratio, Taguchi DOE and Mean analysis using Minitab software. Conclusions were drawn considering the Strength to weight ratio, safety factors to determine optimal design parameters for cross section and material for the chassis.

Key words: ANSYS APDL coding, Chassis, Minitab, Optimization, Taguchi Method.

Cite this Article: Kiran B N and Jyothisna K Moorthy, Structural Optimization of Four-Wheeler Chassis, International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology (IJMET), 15(4), 2024, pp. 16-39.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJMET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_4/IJMET_15_04_002.pdf

1. INTRODUCTION

The chassis is a vehicle's main structural element, giving different parts including the wheels, engine, gearbox, transmission, and fuel tank stability, strength, and support. It is essential to sectors like manufacturing, logistics, and agriculture since it acts as the primary means of transportation and shields occupants from the elements. In addition, the chassis accommodates twisting on uneven roads, resists shock loads, and absorbs torques from the engine and driveline. The truck frame serves a number of essential purposes for the security and functionality of the vehicle. These include of stiffness, power and control systems, weight distribution, support, safety, and passenger space accommodations.

LITERATURE SURVEY

K. Someswara Rao et al. studied the lightest material for automotive chassis, keeping focus on lightweight materials such as aluminum alloys. Steel alloy ASTM A710, AA6063, and AA7075 were taken in consideration for a robust ladder chassis under high load. The structure frame was modeled using SolidWorks, and ANSYS analysis was conducted using model along with theoretical calculations. [1].

Ramasamy et al. studied vehicular chassis dynamics, identifying high stress areas and torsion stiffness. They used FEA to calculate dynamic properties and validated models between different types of cross sections for a ladder chassis through experimental analysis. The proposed changes were on the different types of cross sections for a ladder chassis. Their aim was to increase strength, reduce vibration, and weight. [2].

Padmanabhan S et al. analyzed a C-section truck frame using mild steel and titanium alloy structures. They found titanium alloy performed better in structural examination, while mild steel had the least deflection deviation. [3].

K Someswara Rao et al. This paper discusses the design process for a two-wheeler electric vehicle chassis using the Taguchi method. The researchers optimized parameters like rod thickness, outer diameter, and materials by their yield strength of using ANSYS. They found that tube outer diameters had minimal impact on the design, suggesting 2018Aluminium alloy for optimal results. [4].

Vijaykumar V. Patel et al. conducted a structural analysis of a truck chassis frame using the Finite Element Method (FEM) to determine the critical point for fatigue failure. The study found that the accuracy of the life projection was influenced by model simplification and numerical solution variations and uncertainty. [5].

Tushar M Patel et al. aimed to find the minimal weight of the Eicher 11.10 chassis using Parametric Creo 3.0 and Ansys. Due to the large number of possible models, extensive modeling and analysis were required. The Taguchi method and Finite element analysis were used to reduce side member weight, reducing resource consumption, production costs, and time. [6].

Ramkrishna Parihar et al. utilized the Taguchi method on Resistance spot welding technique to optimize influencing parameters, using L27 orthogonal arrays. They found that welding time significantly influences tensile shear strength, while welding current is the second most important factor. [7]

Singarajan Nagammal Vijayan et al. studied heavy vehicle chassis design and weight reduction using composite materials like epoxy or carbon. They experimented with cross sections of Box design, C-shaped, or I-shaped types, exposed to the same load as steel chassis. Analytical computing validated mathematical results, and carbon epoxy had little stress and deformation when compared to steel, especially in I-shaped sections. [8]

Nikhil Tidke et al. studied the ideal cross-section and material for a high load-bearing Eicher E2 truck chassis. They found that the rectangular box section is stronger, and Al alloy 6063 is recommended for low loading situations. ASTM 302 is recommended for normal loading C cross sections. [9]

Divyanshu Sharma et al. performed model analysis on virtualized truck chassis frames, vibration values were analysed for five diverse frequencies. It was observed that the vibrations caused deformations and the maximum frequency attained was 105.84 Hz. This Analysis recommends that higher frequencies are safer for objects and the design optimization can hold vibrations through natural frequencies. [10]

Kallappa Khannukar et al. performed a research on chassis dynamic analysis through Analytical and Finite Element Method (FEM). It actually was the optimization of chassis shapes via design parameters and acceleration responses that brought down acceleration levels by 20.24 percent, they estimated. The study was able to evidence the similarity between dynamic chassis characteristics and analytical calculations. [11]

Sumedh Kousadikar et al. used hybrid technique to optimize chassis components using sensitivity analysis and FEM-related Taguchi method. They found slimmer component parameters were optimal for allowed deflection, with section-A, pad height, and flange thickness influencing deflection loading conditions. [13]

Rohan Y Garud et al. reviewed chassis design optimization techniques for better material utilization, weight reduction, and cross section. They found that an 8mm thick chassis with high-strength steel yielded better results than a 5mm thick steel chassis. Geometry topology changes were made. [14]

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Ladder chassis are used in Heavy duty vehicles and often have I and C cross sections. Traditionally the most popular materials used to construct chassis are Steel. The major focus in the truck manufacturing industries is to design vehicles with more payload capacity. Using high strength steels enables to corresponding increase in payload capacity. steel has higher yield strength, ductility and tensile strength and is 4 times stronger than Aluminium. In India, there is varying load of goods and passengers which are above even the capacity, hence there are possibilities of failure/fracture in the chassis/frame. Therefore, Chassis with high strength cross section is required to minimize the failures. Factor of safety should be above the standards levels. To increase the strength to Weight ratio and achieve maximum stiffness and strength, The chassis frame is modelled with two C section side rails and are joined with a series of rectangular block cross members. Geometric area of the chassis can be optimized to achieve better performance and reduce fuel consumption. The problem to be addressed in this study is to Optimize the chassis by Design and Analysis using Taguchi DOE, Ansys APDL software and using Statistical analysis using Minitab.

4. OBJECTIVE

The aim of this work is to achieve High strength-to-weight ratio chassis, subsequently optimizing the size of the chassis thereby reducing the weight to increase performance, to ensure proper service life with maximum stiffness and strength. The chassis frame is modelled with two side members joined with a series of rectangular cross members. The cross-section and sizes of the side members and yield stress of the respective material are the control factors. The component should withstand all the forces acting on it without rupture or failure or undue deformation that might render the component incapable during its service life because of a mishap due to sudden failure during operation. An attempt to evolve an improved design resisting the failure and in turn enhancing the life would be the objective for this dissertation work.

The key objectives for this work are stated below:

- Construct models using Ansys APDL Software
- Taguchi method to construct the design of experiment (DOE)
- Perform Structural Analysis using APDL Software
- Perform Statistical Analysis using Taguchi DOE in Minitab Software and retrieve optimized levels for respective parameters
- Validation of result between Taguchi based method and ANSYS for the optimized dimensions.

5. METHODOLOGY

The Chassis model is constructed with the stated dimensions with two C-section side rails and rectangular cross members, using ANSYS Parametric Design Language (APDL). Here cross sections of the side rails and different steel materials are considered as the design parameters, and Taguchi DOE method is used for optimization. FEA analysis and model parameterization are done in APDL. This study uses APDL-based FEA to analyze stress and deformation parameters, Signal to Noise ratio, Taguchi DOE and Mean analysis using Minitab software. The dimension specifications of the designed chassis are given below.

Table 1: Ladder Chassis Dimension

Dimensional Specifications	
Side member cross section	210mm * 76mm * 6mm
Frontal Overhang	935mm
Backward Overhang	1620mm
Wheel Base	3800mm
Width of chassis	2250mm

Fig 1: Side member cross section of original model in mm.

Capacity of the chassis = $8000\text{kg} \times 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 = 78480 \text{ N}$

Capacity of the chassis with 1.25 Percent = 98100 N

Load of entire body + engine = 19620 N

Total load applied on single side member = $98100\text{N} + 19620\text{N} = 117720\text{N}$

As the ladder chassis has 2 side members, therefore load acting on each side member is = $\frac{117720}{2} = 58860\text{N}$.

5.1. Reaction force, shear force and bending moment analysis

Fig 2: Loading diagram.

Fig 3: Shear Force drawing.

Fig 4: Bending moment drawing.

5.2. Taguchi DOE

Taguchi. Geometric optimization is used to identify weight reduction parameters, The Taguchi DOE method implements robust design of experiments and enables produce high quality design at low cost with lesser number of experiments when compared to full factorial methods. Selection of control factors and their levels are done based on literature reviews. Four control factors such as Upper flange thickness, lower flange thickness, web thickness and Yield stress of the Material are selected for the study. Each of the four control factors are treated at 5 Levels. 5 levels are selected to find highly influential performance characteristics.

An Orthogonal Array is a fractional factorial design with balancing properties. With Orthogonal Array, multiple parameters can be estimated simultaneously with reduced number of experiments. A L25 standard Orthogonal Array is used for investigating the S/N ratio. S/N ratios are of 3 types, 1. Smaller is the better, 2. Nominal is the better and 3. larger is the better.

5.3. Steps carried out in Taguchi Method

Structural Optimization of Four-Wheeler Chassis

- Identify the principle/target functions and its reactions.
- Find the testing conditions, quality attributes and noise factors.
- Find the levels and their control factors.
- Choose a suitable Orthogonal Array and build the Matrix.
- Carryout the experiments.

Table 2: Generic orthogonal array.

Number of levels		Number of Parameters								
		2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
2		L4	L4	L8	L8	L8	L8	L12	L12	L12
3		L9	L9	L9	L18	L18	L18	L18	L27	L27
4		L16	L16	L16	L16	L32	L32	L32	L32	L32
5		L25	L25	L25	L25	L25	L50	L50	L50	L50

Fig 5: Flow chart of experiment.

Table 3: Material Properties

Material properties	Structural Steel AISI 1015. ^[16]	ASTM A710 Steel. ^[11]	Mild Steel. ^[17]	High Carbon Steel AISI 1065. ^[18]	ASTM A148 Gr 80–50 mild steel. ^[21]
Density (kg/m ³)	7833.409	7800	7870	7850	7830
Young's Modulus (MPa)	205	205	205	200	210
Poisson's ratio	0.3	0.29	0.29	0.285	0.3
Yield stress (MPa)	325	585	370	490	360

5.4. Coding of the chassis in ANSYS APDL

```

/GRAPH,POWER      ! Graphics control commands
/GST,ON
.
/CPLANE,1
/REPLOT,RESIZE
.
KEYW,PR_SET,1
KEYW,PR_STRUC,1  ! Keyword control commands
.
.
/PREP7
ET,1,BEAM188      ! Defining Element type
.
MPDATA,EX,1,,205000  ! Defining Young's modulus
MPDATA,PRXY,1,,0.29  ! Defining Poisson's ratio
.
MPDATA,DENS,1,,0.0000078  ! Defining Density
SECTYPE, 1, BEAM, CHAN, Side member, 0
SECOFFSET, CENT
SECDATA,76,76,210,6,6,6,0,0,0,0,0  ! Defining the Chassis dimensions
.
K,1,0,0,0,      ! Modelling of the chassis
K,2,350,0,0,
K,3,935,0,0,
.
LSTR, 6, 14
LSTR, 7, 15
.
LMESH,P51X      ! Meshing
/SHRINK,0
.
FLST,2,2,4,ORDE,2  ! Boundary Conditions on model
FITEM,2,16
FITEM,2,19
.
FLST,2,14,4,ORDE,2
.
.
SFBEAM,P51X,1,PRES,9.26,9.26, , , ,0  ! Pressure on beam
FLST,2,105,2,ORDE,2
FITEM,2,1

```

```

FITEM,2,-105
SFBEAM,P51X,1,PRES,9.26,9.26, , , ,0
/STATUS,SOLU
SOLVE
FINISH
    
```


Fig 6: Meshed model in APDL

Table 4: Taguchi DOE Factors and Levels

Factors	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Web (mm)	3	4	5	6	7
Upper Flange (mm)	3	4	5	6	7
Lower Flange (mm)	3	4	5	6	7
Yield stress (MPa)	325	585	370	490	360

5.5. ANSYS APDL Structural Analysis with DOE

Structural analysis is performed by using specifically made tables referred to as "Orthogonal arrays (OA)," Here L25 Orthogonal array is taken into consideration for total number of experiments. Construction of models followed by Structural analysis is then done using Ansys APDL Software for all the 25 experiments identified by Taguchi Design of experiments (DOE). Structural analysis is performed through the below listed processes.

- Manual calculation and theoretical Analysis
- Identify Taguchi DOE
- Construct models using Ansys APDL Software
- Perform Structural Analysis using APDL Software

Table 5: Design of Experiments

Sl.no	Lower Flange (mm)	Upper Flange (mm)	Web (mm)	Yield stress (MPa)
1	3	3	3	325
2	4	4	3	585
3	5	5	3	370
4	6	6	3	490
5	7	7	3	360
6	4	3	4	370
7	5	4	4	490
8	6	5	4	360
9	7	6	4	325
10	3	7	4	585
11	5	3	5	360
12	6	4	5	325
13	7	5	5	585
14	3	6	5	370
15	4	7	5	490
16	6	3	6	585
17	7	4	6	370
18	3	5	6	490
19	4	6	6	360
20	5	7	6	325
21	7	3	7	490
22	3	4	7	360
23	4	5	7	325
24	5	6	7	585
25	6	7	7	370

5.6. FEA based Deformation and von Mises stress results

Fig 7: Experiment 1 results.

Fig 8: Experiment 2 results.

Structural Optimization of Four-Wheeler Chassis

Fig 9: Experiment 3 results

Fig 10: Experiment 4 results

Fig 11: Experiment 5 results

Fig 12: Experiment 6 results

Fig 13: Experiment 7 results

Fig 14: Experiment 8 results

Fig 15: Experiment 9 results

Fig 16: Experiment 10 results

Fig 17: Experiment 11 results

Fig 18: Experiment 12 results

Fig 19: Experiment 13 results

Fig 20: Experiment 14 results

Structural Optimization of Four-Wheeler Chassis

Fig 21: Experiment 15 results

Fig 22: Experiment 16 results

Fig 23: Experiment 17 results

Fig 24: Experiment 18 results

Fig 25: Experiment 19 results

Fig 26: Experiment 20 results

Fig 27: Experiment 21 results

Fig 28: Experiment 22 results

Fig 29: Experiment 23 results

Fig 30: Experiment 24 results

Fig 31: Experiment 25 results

5.7. Entering the observed details of the control characteristics

Table 6: FEA Experiment Results

Experiment No	Web (mm)	Upper Flange (mm)	Lower Flange (mm)	Yield stress (MPa)	Weight (Kg)	von Mises Stress (MPa)	Deformation (mm)
1	3	3	3	325	1677.39939	175.968	5.8477
2	3	4	4	585	1684.71954	144.872	4.85726
3	3	5	5	370	1714.44286	123.479	4.17713
4	3	6	6	490	1724.65288	107.866	3.77159
5	3	7	7	360	1734.78868	95.9741	3.22576
6	4	3	4	370	1711.43564	156.714	4.84764
7	4	4	5	490	1721.45376	132.038	4.25677
8	4	5	6	360	1731.39866	114.39	3.56343
9	4	6	7	325	1746.48949	101.133	3.26646
10	4	7	3	585	1717.62702	150.191	4.0909
11	5	3	5	360	1728.60577	141.459	4.07839
12	5	4	6	325	1743.49625	121.362	3.65745
13	5	5	7	585	1750.13795	106.548	3.2624
14	5	6	3	370	1744.53841	139.479	3.96001
15	5	7	4	490	1754.27286	120.026	3.57755
16	6	3	6	585	1747.55403	129.071	3.68743
17	6	4	7	370	1777.24108	112.367	3.28051
18	6	5	3	490	1751.77215	130.847	3.97553
19	6	6	4	360	1761.24174	113.612	3.34859
20	6	7	5	325	1775.94731	100.659	3.0832
21	7	3	7	490	1784.29194	118.814	3.39459
22	7	4	3	360	1759.14548	123.542	3.74165
23	7	5	4	325	1773.65101	108.127	3.39347
24	7	6	5	585	1779.76754	96.3868	3.05208
25	7	7	6	370	1809.54364	87.132	2.78063

5.8. Calculation of Strength-to-weight ratio from Factor of safety

Table 7: Strength-to-Weight ratio

Experiment No	Yield stress (MPa)	von Mises Stress (MPa)	Factor of Safety (FOS)	Weight (Kg)	Strength to weight ratio
1	325	175.968	1.846926714	1677.399391	0.001101066
2	585	144.872	4.03804738	1684.719535	0.002396866
3	370	123.479	2.996460937	1714.442857	0.001747775
4	490	107.866	4.542673317	1724.652881	0.002633964
5	360	95.9741	3.751011992	1734.788679	0.00216223
6	370	156.714	2.360988808	1711.435636	0.001379537
7	490	132.038	3.711052879	1721.453755	0.002155767
8	360	114.39	3.147128245	1731.398665	0.00181768
9	325	101.133	3.213590025	1746.489494	0.001840028
10	585	150.191	3.895040315	1717.627018	0.002267687
11	360	141.459	2.54490700	1728.605767	0.001472231
12	325	121.362	2.677938729	1743.496255	0.001535959
13	585	106.548	5.490483163	1750.137948	0.003137172
14	370	139.479	2.652729085	1744.538414	0.001520591
15	490	120.026	4.08244880	1754.272863	0.002327146
16	585	129.071	4.53238915	1747.554026	0.002593562
17	370	112.367	3.292781689	1777.241082	0.001852749
18	490	130.847	3.74483175	1751.772151	0.002137739
19	360	113.612	3.168679365	1761.241739	0.001799117
20	325	100.659	3.228722717	1775.947311	0.001818028
21	490	118.814	4.12409312	1784.291938	0.002311333
22	360	123.542	2.913988765	1759.145476	0.00165648
23	325	108.127	3.00572475	1773.65101	0.001694654
24	585	96.3868	6.06929580	1779.767543	0.003410162
25	370	87.132	4.24643070	1809.543638	0.002346686

In order to obtain maximum strength to weight ratio, Objective function larger is the better has to be used to calculate S/N ratio.

5.9. Formulation of Delta Matrix

A Delta matrix is something that helps in analyzing the difference made by multiple factors on how a product can perform or work. Delta values indicate the increase in response variable for one level of factor compared to another. This helps to get insights into which factors are having a major contribution towards the output.

5.10. Functions of a Delta matrix

It allows one to quantify changes in the effect on performance of any given factor (variable) over a system. By identifying the most influential and important factors, one can focus on optimizing those to improve quality or performance.

By affixing a delta matrix with the response, one can find which factors or factor interactions are relatively more important in improving/ degrading performance. It also gives a clarity on how much each of them affects the output, one would know where to focus. Hence, Delta matrix is a systematic approach that can be used in the Taguchi method to analyze experimental data ultimately identifying key factors and minimizing variability in processes or designs thereby improving quality and performance.

Table 8: Delta matrix (Strength-to-Weight ratio)

Level	Thickness of Web (mm)	Thickness of Upper flange (mm)	Thickness of Lower flange (mm)	Yield Stress (MPa)
1	-54.32	-55.49	-55.49	-56.07
2	-54.59	-54.45	-54.52	-55.05
3	-54.4	-53.77	-53.85	-55.19
4	-53.89	-53.38	-53.4	-52.74
5	-53.14	-53.25	-53.09	-51.29
Delta	1.45	2.24	2.4	4.79
Rank	4	3	2	1

Table 9: Delta matrix (Weight)

Level	Thickness of Web (mm)	Thickness of Upper flange (mm)	Thickness of Lower flange (mm)	Yield Stress (MPa)
1	-64.64	-64.76	-64.76	-64.83
2	-64.74	-64.8	-64.79	-64.83
3	-64.83	-64.83	-64.83	-64.87
4	-64.92	-64.87	-64.87	-64.85
5	-65.01	-64.9	-64.9	-64.79
Delta	0.37	0.14	0.14	0.08
Rank	1	2	3	4

Table 10: Delta matrix (Deformation)

Level	Thickness of Web (mm)	Thickness of Upper flange (mm)	Thickness of Lower flange (mm)	Yield Stress (MPa)
1	-12.64	-12.64	-12.6	-11.46
2	-11.97	-11.87	-11.92	-11.08
3	-11.35	-11.27	-11.34	-11.46
4	-10.78	-10.79	-10.81	-11.56
5	-10.25	-10.43	-10.33	-11.45
Delta	2.38	2.21	2.26	0.48
Rank	1	3	2	4

Table 11: Delta matrix (von Mises stress)

Level	Thickness of Web (mm)	Thickness of Upper flange (mm)	Thickness of Lower flange (mm)	Yield Stress (MPa)
1	-42.05	-43.11	-43.1	-41.48
2	-42.22	-42.03	-42.1	-41.35
3	-41.94	-41.31	-41.4	-41.69
4	-41.35	-40.89	-40.91	-41.7
5	-40.5	-40.72	-40.56	-41.84
Delta	1.72	2.38	2.54	0.49
Rank	3	2	1	4

5.11. Analysis using Minitab

Statistical Analysis is done on the FEM results obtained using ANSYS APDL. Von Mises stress, Total deformation and Strength-to-Weight ratio based Signal-to-Noise ratio is measured using Minitab software. The impact of each parameter (Upper flange thickness, Lower flange thickness, web thickness and Material) of truck ladder chassis is then analysed using the Signal to Noise ratio and the delta matrix is obtained, the optimum combination is obtained by choosing the objective function the smaller is the better, for weight, von Mises stress and deformation and objective function the larger is the better for Strength-to-weight ratio.

5.11.1. Weight

Fig 32: Mean effect and SN ratio plot for weight

5.11.2. von Mises stress

Fig 33: Mean effect and SN ratio plot for von Mises stress

5.11.3. Deformation

Fig 34: Mean effect and SN ratio plot for deformation

The calculation of deflection in a member is not carried out by the considering influence factor or dynamic effect but only under sustained load causing deflection. Maximum deflection for beam should not exceed span/325 in general. For steel beams, a typical value for the limit of deflection should be expressed as fraction (for example 1/240 or L/360 depending on application, place, and their code) to span length.

Considering L/325, the allowable deformation in the beam is 19.55mm. Based on the plots obtained from Taguchi analysis for web, upper flange, and lower flange; maximum deflection is around 4.4 mm. Hence the deflection is within the safe limit.

5.11.4. Strength-to-Weight ratio

Fig 35: Mean effect and SN ratio plot for Strength-to-Weight ratio

5.12. Validation Of Taguchi Result for von Mises stress

The main effects plot for means against von Mises stress will provide the approximate value of the working stress each material with respective yield stress will undergo for the given loading conditions on the modelled chassis.

Main Effects Plot for Means

Data Means

Fig 36: Determination of the working stress from mean effect plot

Main Effects Plot for SN ratios

Data Means

Signal-to-noise: Smaller is better

Fig 37: Determination of SN ratio of working stress from SN ratio plot

Hence the Safety factor for identified ASTM A710 Steel with 585MPa yield stress is given by:

$$\frac{\text{Yield stress}}{\text{Working stress}} = \frac{585}{125.414} = 4.66$$

Table 12: Optimum Values Obtained

Objective function	Web (mm)	Upper flange (mm)	Lower Flange (mm)
Values of parameters whose levels induce stress lesser than the working stress	6	5	5
	7	6	6
	-	7	7
Ascending order of levels taken for weight reduction	3	3	3
	4	4	4
	5	5	5
	6	6	6
	7	7	7
Optimum values obtained	6	5	5

Fig 38: Taguchi predictions for von Mises stress on optimized model.

Fig 39: Original model with 6mm each for Web, Upper flange, and Lower flange.

Fig 40: Modified model with 5mm each for upper flange, Lower flange and 6mm for Web.

Table 13: Final obtained results

von Mises stress (MPa)		
Optimized Model - Taguchi based results	Optimized Model - FEA results	Percentage Variation
111.961	102.876	8.1%
Reduction in Weight of chassis (kg)		
Original weight of chassis	Weight of Optimized model	Weight reduction
1768.370	1754.493	13.88

6. CONCLUSIONS

Optimization of the four-wheeler chassis has been done based on higher Strength-to-weight ratio by selecting optimum material using Taguchi method. Weight reduction is done subsequently by parametric optimization of web, upper flange and lower flange of C section of the chassis. The following conclusions have been made based on the above experimental analysis.

- A710 Steel has the highest Strength-to-Weight ratio and improves the overall power and performance with reduced product weight which ultimately increases efficiency with greater payloads.
- APDL based coding has helped in automating model design and reduced time and effort required to design model and FEA analysis.
- Taguchi based analysis using Minitab has drastically reduced the time and effort needed to obtain the optimum value of the control factors.
- Based on the results, Web thickness of 6 mm, Upper Flange thickness of 5 mm thickness and Lower flange thickness of 5 mm are optimal parameters.
- Designed Chassis has high Safety factor of 4.66. hence, the structure is robust enough to handle unforeseen stress, payloads, vibrations and shock with greater durability and attenuates failure. This makes it suitable choice for Heavy duty trucks and transport.
- Reduction in weight of 13.88 kg has been achieved by remodelling the chassis according to the optimum dimension obtained while also ensuring that the induced von Mises stress is below the working stress.

REFERENCES

Journal Papers:

- [1] K. Someswara Rao, K. Pradeep Kumar, B. Sai Kumar, D. Suseel, R. Hari Krishnan, "Design and analysis of light weighted chassis", International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology (IJMET) Volume 8, Issue 5, May 2017,
- [2] Ramasamy. R and Nesalingam R, J. Ashok, M. Jeganathan , "Design and optimization of truck chassis", International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Technology (IJARET), Volume 10, Issue 1, January-February 2019.
- [3] Padmanabhan S, Harsha Vardhan Reddy and Sri Charan Undamatla. "Design and Structural Analysis of Truck Frame", IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering, 2020,
- [4] Someswara Rao, "Design of chassis of two-wheeled electrical vehicle by optimization of design parameters using taguchi method". (IJMET)Volume 8, Issue 4, 2017,
- [5] Vijaykumar V. Patel and R. I. Patel, "Structural analysis of a ladder chassis frame", World Journal of Science and Technology, 2012,
- [6] Tushar M Patel, Dr N M Bhatt, "FEM based Taguchi method to Reduce the Automobile Structural Member Weight", GIT-Journal of Engineering and Technology, Eighth Volume, 2015,
- [7] Ramkrishna Parihar, Sanjay Jathar, "Application of taguchi method to optimize tensile shear strength between stainless steel AISI304 and mild steel", (IJMET) Volume 6, Issue 10, Oct 2015,
- [8] Singarajan Nagammal Vijayan and Sathivelu Sendhilkumar. "Structural Analysis of Automotive Chassis Considering Cross-Section and Material." Int. J. Mech. Eng. Autom". 2015,
- [9] Nikhil Tidke, D. H. Burande, "Analysis of HCV Chassis using FEA", International Engineering Research Journal, Special Edition PGCON-MECH-2017,

- [10] Divyanshu Sharma, Y D Vora, “Design and vibration analysis of heavy duty vehicle (trailer) chassis through FEM software”, International Journal of Engineering Science Invention Research & Development; Vol. III, Issue XI, May 2017
- [11] Kallappa Khannukar, Vinayak Kallannavar, Dr. B. S. Manjunath, “Dynamic analysis of automotive chassis using FEA”, Volume: 02 Issue: 09 | Dec-2015
- [12] Vilas kanaje, Dr. Rachayya Arakerimath “Modal analysis and optimization of heavy duty vehicle chassis” International Engineering Research Journal (IERJ), ISSN 2395-1621, 2015,
- [13] “Effect of Geometrical Parameters on Deflection of Different Chassis Component Sections”, MATEC Web of Conferences 95, 03008 (2017).
- [14] Rohan Y Garud, “Structural Analysis of Automotive Chassis, Design Modification and Optimization”. International Journal of Applied Engineering Research ISSN 0973-4562, 2018
- [15] Sanchit Shrivastava “Design and Analysis of Heavy Commercial Vehicle Chassis Through Material Optimization” ISSN: 2231-5381
- [16] Vyom Bhushan “Design and analysis of 30-ton trailer chassis frame to reduce pollution by decreasing the emission through weight reduction using advanced lightweight material”. International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology (IJMET) ISSN 0976-6340 and ISSN: 0976-6359
- [17] S Satish, “Design and analysis of mild steel mini truck body for increasing the payload capacity”. Elsevier BV
- [18] Snunkhaem Echaroj, “Development of Vehicle Chassis from Novel Materials for Light Weight Electric Shuttles Using Finite Element Analysis”. Science & Technology Asia P-ISSN 2586-9000
- [19] Naman Shah “Analysis and Optimization of a Product Carrier for Weight Reduction”. International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Technology (IJARET)
- [20] A. Agarwal “Structural analysis and weight optimization of automotive chassis by Latin hypercube sampling using metal matrix composites.” scientific committee of the International Conference on Latest Developments in Materials & Manufacturing- 2214-7853
- [21] Alelign Kerebih Jembere “Stress analysis of different cross-section for passenger truck chassis with a material of ASTM A148 Gr 80–50” - 2214-7853
- [22] M. Ibrahim, D.A.Crolla and D.C. Barton, “Effect of Frame Flexibility on the Ride Vibration of Trucks”, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Leeds LS2 9JT, U.K. August 1994. Design and Analysis of Heavy Commercial Vehicle Chassis Through Material Optimization
- [23] Bin Zheng “Analysis of Static and Dynamic Characteristics and Lightweight Design of Titanium Alloy Frame”
- [24] S.Naveen Kumar “Design and Analysis of Automobile Chassis by using Alternative Materials” Journal of Xi’an Shiyou University, Natural Science Edition ISSN : 1673-064X
- [25] Harshal D. Shirodkar “Structural Optimization of a Powered Industrial Lift Truck Frame”
- [26] Abhishek Singh “Structural Analysis of Ladder Chassis for Higher Strength”. International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering. ISSN 2250-2459
- [27] Snunkhaem Echaroj, Development of Vehicle Chassis from Novel Materials for Light Weight Electric Shuttles Using Finite Element Analysis. Science & Technology Asia. P-ISSN 2586-9000
- [28] M. Zehsaz , “The Effect of Connection-Plate Thickness on Stress of Truck Chassis with Riveted and Welded Joints under Dynamic Loads”. Asia Journal of Applied Science. ISSN 1996-3343
- [29] M. F. Spotts, “Design of Machine Elements”, Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi, 2004
- [30] Reddy J.N, “An Introduction to Finite Element Method”, Tata McGraw-Hill Publication, Fifth Edition

Books:

- [31] [1] Theory reference for mechanics APDL and mechanical application-ANSYS
[32] [2] F. P. Beer, and E. R. Johnston, "Mechanics of Materials", McGraw Hill

Chapters in Books:

- [33] [3] 14.1: Design of Experiments via Taguchi Methods - Orthogonal Arrays. Stephanie Fraley

Citation: Kiran B N and Jyothsna K Moorthy, Structural Optimization of Four-Wheeler Chassis, International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology (IJMET), 15(4), 2024, pp. 16-39

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJMET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_4/IJMET_15_04_002.pdf

Abstract Link:

https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJMET_15_04_002

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

✉ editor@iaeme.com